

PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Kalmuratova Khurlikha Rustamxodjaevna

Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh,
assistant of the department "Pedagogy and psychology".

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Abstract. *The article explores and examines the system of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the role of preschool educational institutions that ensure the formation of a healthy and developed personality of the child. Furthermore, this article compares the preschool educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan with one of the developed countries of the world, Japan.*

Key words: *public and private preschool educational institutions, quality of education, primary education, aim of preschool education.*

СИСТЕМА ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Аннотация. *В статье исследована и рассмотрена система дошкольного образования Республики Узбекистан и роль дошкольных образовательных учреждений, обеспечивающих формирование здоровой и развитой личности ребенка. Кроме того, в данной статье сравнивается система дошкольного образования Республики Узбекистан с одной из развитых стран мира – Японией.*

Ключевые слова: *государственные и частные дошкольные образовательные учреждения, качество образования, начальное образование, цель дошкольного образования.*

INTRODUCTION

Preschool education is the initial link in the system of lifelong education. It ensures the formation of a healthy, developed personality of the child, awakening a thirst for learning, preparing for systematic learning. Preschool education is provided up to 6–7 years of age in state and non-state preschool institutions and in the family. The purpose of preschool education is to prepare children for school, the formation of a healthy, developed, free personality of the child, the disclosure of his abilities, and the development of a thirst for learning and systematic learning.

MAIN PART

After Uzbekistan gained Independence, large-scale reforms have been carried out in the sphere of education, as in all other systems. To improve the quality of education and bring it to a new level, a number of measures were carried out in the Republic and state programs were adopted. “The first task that concerns the sphere of preschool education, - noted the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, - We must frankly admit that we missed this most important area of work”.

Indeed, if we turn to statistical data, the coverage of children from 1 to 6 years old in preschool educational institutions in the Republic decreased from 35.1 percent in 1991 to 17.3 percent in 2016. During the years of Independence, one of the main reasons for the sharp decline in enrollment of children in preschool educational institutions was the reduction in their number. If throughout the republic in 1991 there were 9834 preschool educational institutions, by 2016

their number decreased to 5138, that is, during these years the number of preschool educational institutions decreased by 47 percent.

The purpose of preschool education is to prepare children for school, the formation of a healthy, developed, free personality of the child, the disclosure of their abilities and the formation of eagerness for systematic learning.

Kindergarten stands out as the first step in a large educational circle. Therefore, in recent years there can be seen more and more steps of the state in this very direction. At the end of 2019, a separate law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On preschool education and upbringing” was adopted. The very name of the law indicates that kindergarten is not only a place for education, but also the upbringing of children.

In recent years, the government has been paying great attention to the development of this industry. In order to effectively implement reforms in this direction, the Ministry of Preschool Education and its territorial departments in the regions were established by the relevant Decree of the President of the Republic. Moreover, in 2017 alone, over a hundred preschool educational institutions were reconstructed and built, and about 200 kindergartens were overhauled. The phased implementation of this work is reflected in the plans for subsequent years. To staff this industry with higher education teachers, a number of activities are being carried out. In particular, special correspondence departments have been opened in the universities of the republic, and the training of teachers and educators has been established in branches of foreign universities.

Fundamental changes in the system of preschool educational institutions have affected their quality and quantity. Thus, at the beginning of 2020, 13,500 preschool educational institutions operated in Uzbekistan. In 2019, the Ministry of Preschool Education increased the coverage of children to 52 percent compared to 37.7 percent in 2018.

In Uzbekistan, the preschool education system implements pedagogical programs of various types that promote the care, careful supervision, education and active health of children from 2 to 7 years old.

Types of preschool education institutions according to their focus in Uzbekistan:

- Nursery, nursery-kindergarten, kindergarten and home kindergarten as a self-sufficient institution or branch;
- An institution of child education with the functions of primary education - a kindergarten-school;
- An educational preschool organization whose priority is the areas of student knowledge - language, sports, artistic and aesthetic development, etc.;
- A kindergarten with compensatory methods, where the priority is to provide qualified correctional assistance to pupils with minor deviations in psychological or physical development;
- A structure for the supervision and restoration of body conditions in weakened children with the implementation of preventive, hygienic and health-improving procedures;
- A combined kindergarten is based on a group of general developmental, compensatory and health-improving profiles in various combinations.

Meanwhile, the modern system of primary education in Japan was formed in the 70s of the XIX century, following Western models. In the second half of the 19th century, Japan became the only non-Western country that managed to modernize without becoming dependent on other

countries. Japan was free to choose the various systems used in the West and adapt them in its own way. Thus, the modern system is based on the Western model, but does not copy the system of any particular country. However, represents a unique combination of Japanese and Western pedagogical ideals. Primary education in Japan has a long history. Until the 15th century, Buddhist monks provided secular education to the children of aristocrats and samurai. In the XVI century, with the development of commerce, the nouveau riche of the merchant class began to convey children to acquaint reading, writing and arithmetic. This is how the tenarai-juku or terakoya schools appeared. In the 17th century, hanko schools were founded for samurai children and, regardless of the hanko system, tenarai-juku and hanko elementary schools. In these schools, the basics of reading and writing were taught to children of the warrior class who were still too juvenile to attend hanko schools. Since the second half of the XVIII century, tenarai-juku for children of non-noble origin, as well as hanko and tenarai-juku for the samurai class have spread throughout Japan.

In present day kindergartens in Japan are not a compulsory step in the education system, so they are all private. They are accepted from the age of 4 (if parents are particularly busy, from the age of three). There are also nurseries from 1 year of age, but a child can be sent to them only if there is a very good reason, upon mandatory application and provision of documents to the commission, which may refuse.

Kindergartens in Japan are divided into public and private. Hoikuen is a state-run nursery school that accepts children from 3 months of age. It is open from 8am to 6pm and half a day on Saturday. To place a child here, you need to justify this with very compelling reasons. In particular, bring documents stating that both parents work more than 4 hours a day. Children are placed here through the municipal department at their place of residence, and payment depends on family income.

Another type of kindergarten is etien. These gardens can be either public or private. Children are here for no more than 7 hours, usually from 9 am to 2 pm, and mother works less than 4 hours a day.

A special place among private gardens is occupied by elite ones, which are under the tutelage of prestigious universities. If a child ends up in such a kindergarten, then there is no need to worry about his future: after it he enters a university school, and from there, without exams, to the University. A university diploma is a guarantee of a prestigious and well-paid job. Therefore, it is very difficult to get into an elite kindergarten. It costs parents a lot of money to admit their child to such an institution, and the child himself must undergo quite complex testing.

What classes are offered in kindergarten? Children are taught to read, count, write, that is, they are prepared for school. If the child does not attend kindergarten, such preparation is carried out by the mother or special “schools”, which resemble clubs and studios for preschoolers. But the main task of a Japanese kindergarten is not educational, but educational: to teach the child to behave in a team. Whereas, in Uzbekistan, the main emphasis is on preparing children for school, focusing on the development of language and mathematical skills, in Japan, preschool education focuses on developing the child's personality, social skills, creativity and independence. In later life he will have to constantly be in some kind of group, and this skill will be necessary. Children are taught to analyze conflicts that arise in games. At the same time, you should try to avoid rivalry,

since the victory of one may mean the “loss of face” of the other. The most productive solution to conflicts, according to the Japanese, is compromise. Even in the ancient Constitution of Japan it was written that the main dignity of a citizen is the ability to avoid contradictions. It is not customary to interfere in children's quarrels. It is believed that this prevents them from learning to live in a group.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be noted that the preschool education systems in Uzbekistan and Japan have significant differences in approaches, goals and organization. Uzbekistan focuses on preparing children for school and academic skills, while Japan strives to develop a child's personality, social skills and creativity. The Japanese education system offers a variety of teaching methods, including play-based learning and project-based learning, as well as active use of games and outdoor activities. In Uzbekistan, preschool education is usually provided through government programs, while in Japan it is compulsory for all children and supported by government subsidies.

Both systems have their advantages and disadvantages, and their further improvement can be aimed at taking into account the best practices and experiences of other countries. Ultimately, the main priority should be to provide quality education and ensure the full development of every child in preschool age.

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